

Maritime Trade between Tamilnadu and South Korea A Study

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A B S T R A C T

There are many similarities between Tamilnadu and South Korea which many people may be unaware of. The main possible reason behind the cultural similarities and the spread of Buddhism to Korea could be because of the Maritime trade between Tamilnadu and Korea. The evidence from Sangam literature and archeological findings prove Tamil people had sea trade links with other countries. Much evidence from the pre-historic port city of Adichanallur in Tamilnadu shows indigenous people traveling to South-East Asia, including Korea, through the ancient seaport Korkai. These ancient trade connections entered a new era when Korean companies started investing in Tamilnadu in the 1990s. This article discusses about the cultural similarities and maritime trade between these two regions.

Key Words: Tamilnadu, South Korea, Buddhism, Archeological, Pre-historic port

Introduction

Maritime Trade between Tamilnadu and South Korea goes back to more than 2000 years. There is much historical evidence, including archeological findings, to show that Tamil people traded across seas with South-East Asian countries, Korea and China. The ancient port of Korkai in Tamilnadu was the hub of maritime trade and had trade links with Korea, and the city was once believed to be the cradle of civilization. The maritime trade had many impacts on both regions, including similarities in food, language, and culture and these trade links are continued even today.

Early maritime trade between Tamilnadu and South Korea

Geographically Tamilnadu is located on the southern border of the Indian Peninsula, and it is surrounded by the Indian Ocean in the south and the Bay of Bengal in the East. Korean Peninsula is located in South-East Asia, and it is bordered by Korean Strait and the East China Sea in the south, the Yellow Sea in the West, and the Sea of Japan in the East. The active sea trade could be the possible reason behind the cultural and linguistic relationship between Tamilnadu and Korea. Ancient Tamilnadu had three kingdoms like, Pandya, Chera, and Chola, including smaller kingdoms. Similarly, Korean Peninsula also has three kingdoms like, Koguryo, Silla, and Paekche, including Gaya territory.

It is believed that the Tamil port of Kayal and the Korean territory of Gaya had maritime trade links. Tamils maintained close cultural and trade relations with China by exporting pearls, corals, beads, and glass vessels. Archaeologists have found Chinese coins made of bronze and copper in many places like Tanjavur and Mahabalipuram. Even though Korea has its own identity, the ancient Tamil's reverence of China most probably also included Korea as well. The spread of Buddhism from ancient Tamilnadu to South-East Asia was made possible through this Maritime Trade between Tamilnadu and South Korea.

Archaeological proof of Tamil Maritime trade

Adichanallur, a pre-historic harbor site in Tamil Nadu, is considered the cradle of Iron Age civilization. Researchers examined five skulls from the site in 1986 and found three significant races: Proto-Australoids and Mediterranean ancestors. They compared the skeletal

data to populations worldwide, revealing additional racial groupings in the region, including Caucasoids, Mongoloids, Negroids, Australoids, Dravidians, and Mixed Traits.

The Tamil proverb "YaadhumOoreYaavarumKelir" highlights Tamils' sense of kinship with all locations and people. Indigenous people from North and South-East Asia visited the ancient port of Korkai in Tamil Nadu for commercial purposes, highlighting the ancient maritime trade between Tamilnadu and South Korea.

Spread of Buddhism from Ancient Tamilnadu to South Korea

From the first century BCE till the fifth century CE, Buddhism was the most practiced religion in Tamil Nadu. Chilappadiharam, Manimekalai, and Kundalakesi are the literary works from the early days of Tamil literature that mention the development of Buddhism in the East. Buddhism was first introduced to the Koguryo kingdom in 372 CE, then to the Paekche kingdom in 384 CE, and then, between 527 and 535 CE, to the Silla kingdom. Buddhism practiced in Tamil Nadu and Korea from the first century BCE to the fifth century CE shows some similarities with the old Maritime Trade between Tamilnadu and South Korea. According to many scholars, Indian traders, through their maritime trade, were responsible for the introduction of Buddhism in Korea.

The traders have been believed to be from Tamilnadu, and the reason for this is that incense is one of the most important goods that Tamilians exported to China and other South-eastern countries. In A.D. 417, during the reign of King Nulchi, it was said that an Indian monk traveled to Silla in Korea through Koguryo. He is known by the names A-do and Mukho-ja, which both indicate "dark, complex foreigner." So, most likely, he may be from South India and especially from Tamilnadu.

The cultural influence of Tamilnadu and South Korea

Tamilians must have arrived in South Korea for sea trade in the first century B.C. In popular legend, Princess Heo Hwang-ok, from the Ayuta, arrived by boat in Gaya with her twin fish which is the country's emblem. After her marriage to King Suro, she ruled as the first queen of the Gaya kingdom. Many researchers believe that Ayuta was the city of Ayodhya in Uttar Pradesh. However, there are more and more reasons to believe that she was from Tamil Nadu, specifically the Pandyan or Aai dynasty.

Linguistic similarities between Tamil and Korean languages are crucial for understanding the history of maritime trade between Tamilnadu and South Korea. Nearly 500 words share similar pronunciations and meanings, such as 'Appa', grass, and day. Koreans and Tamils share common culture and traditions, including rice as a staple food, ancestor worship, and animal sacrifice. Both regions practice MunnoorVazhipaadu, ancestor worship, and animal sacrifice, with Ayyanar temples resembling Buddha temples in Korea's countryside. Tamil people perform Kummi dance during Pongal harvest festival, resembling Korean Ganggansullae and Tamilnadu's 'Thappaattam' in cultural symbolism. Tamilians play 'Pannangal,' which is exactly similar to the 'Gonggi' game played by Koreans. The rules of the game played by Tamilians and Koreans are similar, and the only difference is that in Tamilnadu, people use stones, and in Korea, people use pebbles.

Cultural exchange between Tamilnadu and South Korea in recent years

Food is the next one to come after trade and commerce. Arirang, which was opened in Chennai in 2004, was among the first Korean restaurants. Now in Chennai, there are at least six Korean restaurants serving traditional dishes like bibimbap, which consists of rice with vegetables, bees, and chili pepper paste.

InKo, supported by TVS and Hyundai, works to foster cultural exchange between Koreans and Indians. InKo is a non-profit center for culture and information, and it also arranges Korean language classes for Indians and English language classes for Koreans to assist in closing the communication gap. Local residents enrolling in Korean classes have also increased in InKo. University students from Korea also travel to Chennai to actively take part in volunteerism initiatives like Happy Move Volunteers.

They engage in a variety of social and cultural activities, including teaching at public schools, organizing clean-up drives, constructing restrooms, and more. In the past seven years, more than 4,000 Korean students who participated in this program have traveled to and volunteered in India. The Kancheepuram district of Tamil Nadu has profited from its efforts, as over 200 schools and 100,000 students have benefited from this program. It is interesting to note that the University of Korea, which previously offered a degree program in Hindi, has now added a course in Tamil. A Korean translation of Thirukkural's ancient Tamil literary work is currently being completed.

Modern-day trade between Tamilnadu and South Korea

Tamilnadu, India's fourth-largest state, has a diverse manufacturing sector with high factories and industrial workers. Its maritime route connects South Korea and Tamil Nadu, with Chennai Port handling significant cargo volumes and connecting to global destinations like South Korea. The Port of Busan, a busiest port in the world, is a vital hub for maritime trade in the region. It serves as a gateway for South Korean goods destined for Tamil Nadu and other parts of India.

South Korea's economic growth is driven by an export-based model, focusing on high-tech goods like semiconductors, automobiles, machinery, and wireless communication devices. The country has a significant shipbuilding industry and a significant auto production capacity.

Tamilnadu and South Korea have long-standing ties, with Hyundai establishing a plant in 1996. Chennai has become a manufacturing hub for many Korean companies like Samsung, LG, Kotra, and Lotte, etc. According to the Consulate General of the Republic of Korea in Chennai, there are more than 300 Korean companies in Chennai with more than 5000 people. Data shows that the largest expatriate community in Chennai is the Korean community.

One of the reasons for Korean companies to choose Chennai is because the Chennai port is the nearest Indian port to Korea. The city and Tamilnadu have many engineering colleges with better quality of education. The maximum trade between these two regions is in Auto and Electronics. The electronics major Samsung has one of its manufacturing facilities in Tamilnadu. There are some textile-related Korean companies in Tirupur and Korean shops and restaurants in Sriperumbudur. Today Korean products are found in every household and office and Korean automobile companies manufacture every fifth car running on the Tamilnadu's streets.

Conclusion

Many people are unaware of the various similarities between the Tamil and Korean civilizations. Historical evidence proves that the ancient Tamils were mariners who traded across the oceans with various nations, including those in South East Asia. Language and

cultural similarities between India and Korea can be largely attributable to marine trade relations between the Pandyan kingdom of Tamil Nadu and Korea 2000 years ago. The maritime trade between South Korea and Tamil Nadu has played a significant role in fostering economic growth and cooperation between the two regions. Like in the past, the future will also be facilitated by the exchange of goods, technology, and expertise, contributing to the development of industries and economies in Tamilnadu and South Korea.

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